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**Generalization of An Er's
Matrix Method for
Computing**

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GENERALIZATION OF AN ER'S MATRIX METHOD FOR COMPUTING

Er's matrix method for computing Fibonacci numbers and their sums can be extended to the s -additive sequence:

$$g_{-s+1} = g_{-s+2} = \dots = g_{-1} = 0, \quad g_0 = 1,$$

and

$$g_n = \sum_{i=1}^s g_{n-i} \quad \text{for } n > 0.$$

For example, if we note $S_n = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} g_j$, we define two $(s+1) \times (s+1)$ matrixes such that:

$$B_n = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ S_n & g_n & g_{n-1} & \dots & g_{n-s+2} & g_{n-s+1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots \\ S_{n-s+1} & g_{n-s+1} & g_{n-s} & \dots & g_{n-2s+3} & g_{n-2s+2} \end{bmatrix},$$

$n \geq 1$, and

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

thus, we have analogously:

$$B_{n+1} = M^{n+1}, \quad M^{r+c} = M^r \cdot M^c,$$

whence

$$\begin{aligned} S_{r+c} &= S_r + g_r S_c + g_{r-1} S_{c-1} + \dots + g_{r-s+1} S_{c-s+1}, \\ g_{r+c} &= g_r g_c + g_{r-1} g_{c-1} + \dots + g_{r-s+1} g_{c-s+1}, \end{aligned}$$

and for $r = c = n$ it results:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{2n} &= S_n + g_n S_n + g_{n-1} S_{n-1} + \dots + g_{n-s+1} S_{n-s+1}, \\ g_{2n} &= g_n^2 + g_{n-1}^2 + \dots + g_{n-s+1}^2; \end{aligned}$$

for $r = n$, $c = n-1$, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} g_{2n-1} &= g_n g_{n-1} + g_{n-1} g_{n-2} + \dots + g_{n-s+1} g_{n-s}, \quad \text{etc.} \\ S_{2n-1} &= S_n + g_n S_{n-1} + g_{n-1} S_{n-2} + \dots + g_{n-s+1} S_{n-s} \end{aligned}$$

Whence we can construct a similar algorithm as M. C. Er for computing s-additive numbers and their sums.

REFERENCE:

M. C. Er, Fast Computation of Fibonacci Numbers and Their Sums, J. Inf. Optimization Sci. (Delhi), Vol. 6 (1985), No. 1. pp. 41-47.

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